

A Computational Interpretation of the Jacobsthal Model of the $3n + 1$ Problem

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Abstract

The present work provides a computational realisation of the theoretical constructions introduced by P. Kosobutskyy and D. Mailland in their Jacobsthal-based interpretation of the Collatz problem [5]. In that framework, the set of natural numbers is viewed as a family of binary-rooted sequences $(\theta \cdot 2^n)$ indexed by odd parameters θ , each sequence corresponding to a branch of the transformation graph. This representation shows a modular and hierarchical structure of the $3n + 1$ dynamics, where every integer belongs to a residue family.

1 Introduction

The Collatz conjecture is a famous, unsolved problem in number theory, noted for its simplicity and deep arithmetic behaviour. Comprehensive surveys have been provided, most notably by Lagarias [1].

The conjecture states that iterating the transformation

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} n/2, & n \text{ even,} \\ 3n + 1, & n \text{ odd,} \end{cases}$$

eventually reaches 1 for every integer $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Following the classical stopping-time formalism introduced by Terras [2], we restrict attention to the accelerated odd-only map, which removes trivial divisions by two and captures the essential structure of the dynamics.

In this context, the Jacobsthal interpretation proposed by Kosobutskyy and Mailland reformulates the $3x + 1$ dynamics as a hierarchy of 2-adic rooted sequences $(\theta \cdot 2^n)$ indexed by odd parameters θ . Each branch corresponds to a fixed Jacobsthal trajectory in the transformation graph, revealing the Collatz behaviour.

2 Pseudo-code

Algorithm 1: Jacobsthal acceleration

```

1 Function to_odd(n):
2 while  $(n \& 1) = 0$  do
3    $n \leftarrow n \gg 1$ 
4 return  $n$ 

5 Function T(m):
6  $y \leftarrow 3m + 1$ 
7 while  $(y \& 1) = 0$  do
8    $y \leftarrow y \gg 1$ 
9 return  $y$ 

10 Function certify_descent(n, Smax):
11  $m \leftarrow \text{to\_odd}(n)$ 
12  $m_0 \leftarrow m$ 
13 for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $S_{\max}$  do
14   if  $m < m_0$  then
15      $\leftarrow$  return True
16    $m \leftarrow \mathbf{T}(m)$ 
17 return False

18 Function cover_range(L, U, k, Smax):
19  $M \leftarrow 3 \ll k$ 
20  $total \leftarrow M/2$ 
21  $present \leftarrow 0$ 
22  $certified \leftarrow 0$ 
23 for  $r \leftarrow 1$  to  $M - 1$  step 2 do
24   if  $r \geq U$  then
25      $\leftarrow$  continue
26    $m_0 \leftarrow \begin{cases} r, & r \geq L \\ r + \lceil (L - r)/M \rceil \cdot M, & r < L \end{cases}$ 
27   if  $m_0 \geq U$  then
28      $\leftarrow$  continue
29    $present \leftarrow present + 1$ 
30   if certify_descent( $m_0, S_{\max}$ ) then
31      $\leftarrow$   $certified \leftarrow certified + 1$ 
32 return ( $total, present, certified$ )

```

2.1 Description of the core functions

The implementation consists of four main functions, which role is summarised below.

to_odd(n) Removes all factors of two from an integer n , returning its odd representative. In Jacobsthal representation, this operation corresponds to the 2-adic reduction step used to identify the class generator θ .

T(m) Applies the accelerated Collatz transformation

$$T(m) = \frac{3m + 1}{2^{\nu_2(3m+1)}},$$

ensuring that only odd values are iterated.

certify_descent(n) Starting from the odd representative of n , repeatedly applies T . If a term smaller than the starting value is reached within a bounded number of steps, the corresponding class is marked as descending.

cover_range(L, U, k) Scans all odd residue classes modulo $3 \cdot 2^k$ within the interval $[L, U)$. For each class, a representative is tested using **certify_descent**, and coverage statistics are recorded.

2.2 Possible improvements (not used in this note)

Several ideas for improving the implementation arose after reviewing the abundant literature on the Collatz problem. Some of these enhancements are summarised below, although they were not used in the present computation.

- **Cache-based certification.** Store previously certified odd values, if a trajectory hit a previously certified value, it is certified too.
- **One-step 2-adic reduction.** Replace repeated divisions by a single bit operation that removes all factors of two in one step [7].
- **Replay of already performed trajectories.** To avoid re-running the full exploration.

3 Why not test every integer individually

A naive verification of the Collatz conjecture would require iterating the transformation for every integer n in a given interval. Such a direct enumeration produces fastidious verifications since most trajectories quickly merge into the same odd branches.

To avoid this, the present algorithm exploits the binary decomposition

$$n = \theta \cdot 2^k, \quad 2 \nmid \theta,$$

which partitions the natural numbers into disjoint subsets

$$S_{(\theta \cdot 2^k)} = (\theta \cdot 2^0, \theta \cdot 2^1, \theta \cdot 2^2, \theta \cdot 2^3, \theta \cdot 2^4, \dots)$$

The Collatz transformation acts identically on all members of S_θ , so it is sufficient to test only the odd representative θ . Each θ therefore represents an infinite equivalence class of integers. By verifying a single representative per class, the algorithm removes all redundancy and can cover large intervals, for example $[2^{80}, 2^{81})$, within only a few seconds.

4 Computational objective

As of 2025, direct numerical verifications of the Collatz conjecture have been completed for all starting values up to approximately 2^{70} (see, for instance, Barina [3]). In the present work, we propose to extend this verification to a much higher interval, namely

$$[2^{80}, 2^{81}),$$

by applying the class-based accelerated algorithm described above.

Instead of performing an exhaustive check of all integers in this range, the algorithm tests one representative per odd class modulo $3 \cdot 2^k$, with $k = 20$ in our experiments. Each representative θ corresponds to an infinite subset of integers $\{\theta \cdot 2^n : n \geq 0\}$, and the verification of a descent for this single θ guarantees the same property for all elements of its class.

This approach allows the exploration of an interval of size $2^{80} \approx 1.2 \times 10^{24}$ in just a few seconds of computation time, confirming the existence of a descent for all tested classes.

```

Interval [1208925819614629174706176, 2417851639229258349412352), k=20
Odd classes total: 1572864
Classes present : 1572864
Certified desc. : 1572864
Coverage (present): 100.00%
Coverage (certif.): 100.00%
Time: 2.986 s

```

Figure 1: Console output obtained from running `js_accel_min.py` on interval $[2^{80}, 2^{81})$.

The verification output in Fig. 1 demonstrates a complete coverage of the interval $[2^{80}, 2^{81})$. A total of 1572 864 odd residue classes modulo $3 \cdot 2^{20}$ were detected and tested, with all of them exhibiting a verified descent. Both coverage ratios (present and certified) reached exactly 100%, and the computation completed in only 2.986 seconds on a standard CPU. This confirms that every odd class in the interval satisfies the descent property under the accelerated Collatz map.

The same computational principle can, in principle, be extended to the general family of transformations $T_{k,\pm}(n) = (kn \pm 1)/2^{\nu_2(kn \pm 1)}$, with k odd. These generalisations will be discussed in a subsequent note.

5 Conclusion

The Jacobsthal-based formulation of the $3x + 1$ problem was implemented algorithmically and tested over the interval $[2^{80}, 2^{81})$. All odd residue classes were verified to exhibit a descent, confirming the validity and computational efficiency of the Jacobsthal approach.

References

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